

TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF SYMPTOMS OF DIFFUSE TOXIC GOITER

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Abstract. Diffuse toxic goiter is a pathology associated with the functioning of the endocrine system. Its essence is that some autoimmune processes lead to an increase in the production of thyroid hormones. Against this background, thyrotoxicosis occurs - simply put, this is poisoning of the body with hormones produced by the thyroid gland.

Key words: diffuse toxic goiter, symptoms, manifestations, prevention.

ЛЕЧЕНИЕ И ПРОФИЛАКТИКА СИМПТОМОВ ДИФФУЗНОГО ТОКСИЧЕСКОГО ЗОБА

Аннотация. Диффузный токсический зоб – патология, связанная с функционированием эндокринной системы. Суть его в том, что некоторые аутоиммунные процессы приводят к увеличению выработки гормонов щитовидной железы. На этом фоне возникает тиреотоксикоз – проще говоря, это отравление организма гормонами, вырабатываемыми щитовидной железой.

Ключевые слова: диффузный токсический зоб, симптомы, проявления, профилактика.

Symptoms of diffuse toxic goiter include:

increased body temperature;

increased sweating; the patient always feels hot;

cardiopalmus;

increased blood pressure;

weakness in arms and legs;

dermatological manifestations. As a result, the nails may break and the hair may fall out a lot. Sometimes there is a change in the color of some areas of the skin and darkening of others. Usually the integument is dark on the elbows, lower back and neck;

changes in behavior. For example, a person becomes more restless and tense.

bulging eyes (bulging eyes). This is common, but not necessary;

tears, feeling that there is something extra in the eyes (garbage, sand);

enlargement of the thyroid gland (this is called a goiter);

severe weight loss, which is especially noticeable in initially overweight people.

Often women face this disease. According to various sources, they get sick 5-6 or even 8-9 times more often than men. There is also a dependence on the place of residence. Toxic goiter is most actively detected in women living in big cities.

Reasons

It is very difficult to say why diffuse goiter appears and endocrine diseases appear. Currently, medicine does not have a clear answer to this question. But there are some factors that contribute to the appearance of "toxic" goiter: heredity. It is noted that if one of the close relatives is sick, the risk of the disease is high;

bad ecology. Obviously, this is why we often talk about large cities with more polluted air than other settlements;

infections;

psychotrauma. Stress is also a symptom of big cities;

poor quality food. In particular, people who do not get enough iodine from food or, on the contrary, have an excessive amount of iodine, are at risk;

other autoimmune diseases;

smoking. Studies show that this problem occurs twice as often in smokers than in people who lead a healthy lifestyle.

Usually, after talking to the patient, it becomes clear that diffuse toxic goiter is caused by a combination of several factors.

Levels or stages

Diffuse toxic goitre There are three stages (levels) of disease development. A mild case is accompanied by a relatively small tachycardia (up to a hundred beats per minute), as well as anxiety.

The severe level of toxic goiter is characterized by severe fatigue, disruption of the functioning of various organs, as well as body systems. Such a condition does not appear suddenly - we are talking about a problem that has been ignored and has not been treated, even if we take into account that it has manifested itself for a long time.

There are other classifications that evaluate diffuse goitre according to its size, level of palpation, etc.

Complications and consequences

Without treatment of diffuse toxic goiter, the patient's condition is always complicated. We are talking about pathologies of heart, blood vessels, central nervous system and gastrointestinal diseases. In difficult situations, there is a risk of paralysis. The extreme manifestation of the disease is a thyrotoxic crisis, as a result of which 30 to 50% of patients die.

However, do not be afraid to make such a diagnosis. If you start treatment on time and follow all the recommendations of doctors, all body functions will be normal - the patient will live a long and very comfortable life.

Diagnostics

Diagnostic measures to determine diffuse toxic goiter include:

visual inspection and palpation. Often suspicions about the disease appear already at the first visit to the doctor;

tests. There is a complete list of them, but do not forget to check the TSH level, as well as T3 and T4;

Ultrasound examination of the examined organ;

scintigraphy. This is a gamma camera study;

Thyroid scan using an MRI machine.

When diagnosing diffuse goitre, it is very important not only to make a correct diagnosis, but also to know in advance the possible complications for a particular patient. For this reason, research is usually comprehensive.

Treatment

Diffuse toxic goiter Consult an endocrinologist for treatment of diffuse toxic goiter. This includes:

use of various drugs. They are prescribed individually - such drugs should never be used without consulting a doctor. In some cases, patients require outpatient treatment;

correction of nutrition. Patients are prescribed a diet aimed at controlling iodine intake;

treatment of diffuse goiter with radioactive iodine;

surgical intervention. After surgery, patients are prescribed lifelong use of certain hormonal drugs.

Treatment of toxic goitre with traditional methods, information about which can be easily found on the Internet, is not a suitable solution in this case. If the disease starts (and it certainly happens without medical help), the health and life of the patient is in danger. Therefore, it is important not to delay a visit to the doctor and seek help immediately at the first symptoms.

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